

METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING CHEMICAL REACTION SPEED WITH MODERN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES

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Annotation: *Methods of teaching the topic of chemical reaction rate using information technology. Such analyzes were performed for the first time.*

Keywords: *Chemical reaction, ICT, pedagogy, technology, laboratory.*

INTRODUCTION

One of the most important methodological principles that allows the effective use of information and communication technologies (ICT) is the integration of computer technology with traditional forms and methods.

Modern electronic textbooks, virtual chemical laboratories, the Internet, new teaching aids are used in the lessons on the rate of chemical reactions. The task of the teacher is to select these funds according to the content of the teaching materials, the age and psychological characteristics of the school students. The use of ICT in the classroom should be goal-oriented and methodologically based.

So, as our lives today are inseparable from the technology that provides information and communication processes, there is a need to create ICT-based education.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The main purpose of this research is to reveal the role and place of information and communication technologies in teaching the topic of chemical reaction rate using information technology.

Chemical reactions are divided into homogeneous and heterogeneous reactions. Homogeneous reactions take place in a homogeneous medium (e.g. in a gas phase or in solution). Heterogeneous reactions take place in different phases (e.g. solid and liquid, solid and gas, liquid and gas).

The rate of a chemical reaction is the number of collisions that occur in a unit of time per unit volume. The rate of a reaction is usually characterized by a change in the concentration of any of the reacting or forming substances per unit time.

Development and analysis of recommendations on the use of information and communication technologies by teachers of chemistry in educational activities and preparation for lessons.

RESULTS

One of the urgent problems of modern education is to prepare students for independent living, to develop their interests, abilities, to realize their life plans. The issues of individualization of reading, activation of knowledge, development of creative abilities of students are of great importance as one of the conditions for their successful socialization.

Based on the above tasks, a number of general requirements are set for modern lessons:

- Arming students with conscious, deep and solid knowledge;
- develop strong skills and abilities that help students prepare for life;
- Improving the effectiveness of education in the classroom, the formation of personal characteristics of students in the educational process;
- Comprehensive development of students, the development of their general and special features;
- to have the skills and abilities to work with books, to study and deepen or supplement knowledge independently, and to develop the ability to apply the acquired knowledge in practice.

To consider the general requirements that a high-quality modern chemistry course must meet, the following are the most important:

1. Use of the latest achievements of chemistry, the creation of a lesson based on the laws of advanced pedagogical, educational process;
2. Implementation of the lesson on the optimal ratio of all didactic principles (scientific, visual, comprehensibility, etc.);
3. The use of interdisciplinary links in the teaching of chemistry in order to form students' natural-scientific imagination;
4. Linking lesson materials with life (practical and daily activities of students), teaching chemical culture to work safely with substances, materials and chemical processes;
5. Ensuring that the chemistry lesson is enriched with bright, interesting, effective theoretical and experimental facts;
6. Clearly design and plan the results of each lesson;
7. Conducting demonstration and laboratory experiments in chemistry classes, as well as special practical training.

CONCLUSION

The modern teacher: explains the teaching material in an interesting and understandable way; able to choose teaching methods; appropriate; positively supports cognitive activity; can have an effective impact on students; develops students, forms new ways of thinking.

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